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ALX3 consensus motifs in mammals.

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In addition to motif discovery for ALX3, we studied consensus motifs for BARHL1/2 and DLX1-5 as well.

Citations

1. McGonnell, I.M., Graham, A., Richardson, J., Fish, J.L., Depew, M.J., Dee, C.T., Holland, P.W. and Takahashi, T., 2011. Evolution of the Alx homeobox gene family: parallel retention and independent loss of the vertebrate Alx3 gene. *Evolution & Development*, 13(4), pp.343-351.